

Introduction: The crystallization of the lunar magma ocean (LMO) resulted in a plagioclase-rich floatation crust, a mafic cumulate mantle, dense Ti-rich ilmenite-bearing cumulates (IBCs), and a reservoir enriched in potassium, rare earth elements, and phosphorus (KREEP). While both models and experimental work broadly agree on the products of magma ocean crystallization, the late-stage evolution of the magma ocean and its products through space and time remain poorly constrained. Here we synthesize recent and ongoing work investigating the evolution and distribution of the late-stage magma ocean, the dense IBCs, and the KREEP-rich material.

Early crust formation: Initial growth of the floatation crust would have begun soon after accretion of the Moon was complete, and continued for a period of up to ~200 Myr [1]. This period coincides with the period of heaviest impact bombardment. The high flux of impacts would have penetrated the thin, still-forming crust, excavating LMO material and mixing it into the surface. Models of this process [4] successfully explain the high FeO content of the mixed feldspathic upper crust [2], the depth to the pure anorthosite below [3], and the highly variable density revealed by small-scale gravity anomalies (Fig. 1; see Gowman & Andrews-Hanna, this meeting). The similarity between the nearside and farside highlands in both the magnitude of the small-scale gravity anomalies and the FeO abundances suggests a similar early history of crustal thickening, indicating that the lunar crustal asymmetry largely post-dates this early epoch of crust formation.

Figure 1. Observed (left) and modeled (right) small-scale gravity anomalies from mixing of LMO into the upper crust during crustal formation.

Magma ocean crystallization and the lunar asymmetry: The prominent topographic and crustal asymmetry between the near and far sides of the Moon was likely established during crustal formation. While the observations above indicate that the asymmetry was not yet established during the time in which the upper ~10 km of the crust formed, it must have been established before the end of crust formation (see below). One possible mechanism for the formation of the asymmetry is from a degree-one

instability of the magma ocean itself [5]. If the bulk density of the LMO exceeded that of the underlying solid interior, the lowest immediately attainable potential energy state would be a lens of LMO in one hemisphere, pinching out to zero thickness in the opposite hemisphere (Fig. 2). This degree-one instability would develop very rapidly due to the low viscosity of the LMO. Subsequent LMO crystallization would thicken the crust primarily in one hemisphere, generating the observed crustal asymmetry.

The density inversion required for this instability is predicted in some thermodynamic models of LMO crystallization [6]. However, experimental work favors a lower density LMO throughout its crystallization [7]. In this case, the density inversion could still occur if the dense cumulates remain suspended in the convecting LMO rather than settling out.

The resulting asymmetry in the magma ocean must eventually reverse in order to explain the observed nearside concentration of KREEP (see below). The decreasing heat flux during continued crustal thickening coupled with the decreasing thickness of the remaining LMO would cause a rapidly declining Rayleigh number, which could lead to crystal settling and a decrease in the net density of the LMO. Once the LMO density was reduced below that of the solid interior, a global, hydrostatic LMO sandwiched between the mantle and crust would result.

Figure 2. Schematic diagram of the formation of the lunar asymmetry from a degree-one magma ocean instability.

Evolution of the late-stage magma ocean: Excavation of the lunar interior by the giant South Pole-Aitken (SPA) basin provides a constraint on the late-stage magma ocean [8]. SPA is surrounded by an asymmetric ejecta blanket, with high concentrations of Th in the southwest ejecta relative to the low-Th northeast ejecta. This observation can be explained by the presence of a thin and discontinuous LMO layer at the time of the impact. For the case of a hydrostatic late-stage LMO trapped between the crust and the mantle, the LMO would be thicker where the crust was thinner. At ~98.8 percent solidification (PCS) this scenario predicts magma ocean to be present below the crust only in the southwestern half of the region in which SPA would form, explaining the elevated Th concentration in the southwest ejecta blanket. As

crystallization proceeded, by 99.9 PCS the LMO would concentrate only beneath the thinnest crust of the nearside, within what would become the Procellarum KREEP terrane (PKT). The predicted distribution of LMO and concentration of Th as a function of PCS are consistent with the timing and Th concentration in the ejecta blankets of SPA and Imbrium [8].

Figure 3. **a** Schematic cross-section showing the effect of crustal thickness on LMO thickness, **b** pre-basin crustal thickness model, and **c-d** LMO thickness at two stages representing SPA formation and the final PKT.

Vertical and lateral distribution of IBCs: At ~ 90 PCS, dense, Ti-rich ilmenite-bearing cumulates are predicted to form. Although these overdense cumulates must at some point sink into the interior, the nature and timing of that overturn is uncertain. SPA contains Ti-rich material within its central melt sheet, which was sourced from depths of up to several hundred kilometers [9]. However, the ejecta of SPA does not show a discernible Ti enhancement [8]. These observations suggest that partial overturn of the IBCs had occurred on the farside at the time of that impact, with IBC-rich material still present in the upper mantle but not as a discrete layer below the crust.

Models suggest that the thermal anomaly from the impact may have triggered a global mantle convection pattern, displacing Ti-rich material within the upper mantle of the farside toward the nearside [10]. Upon reaching the nearside, these overdense cumulates are predicted to sink into the interior in an interconnected pattern of sheet-like downwellings [11]. The predicted pattern of remnants of this Ti-rich material at the base of the crust match the pattern of linear gravity and gravity gradient anomalies encircling the nearside PKT [12]. Collectively, these observations suggest that dense IBCs were distributed through the upper mantle on the lunar farside at the time of the SPA impact, but formed a more concentrated subcrustal layer on the nearside prior to their overturn.

Figure 4. **a** Observed and **b** modeled gravity gradients, showing a polygonal pattern representing remnants of IBCs at the base of the crust after mantle overturn [12].

Final resting place of KREEP: Although KREEP-rich material clearly became concentrated on the nearside, the present-day distribution of this material in the subsurface is uncertain. The surface distribution of Th is dominated by the ejecta of the Imbrium basin, revealing only that KREEP was present in the target at the time of that impact. Models of a thick layer of KREEP throughout the PKT predict strong thermal uplift and elevated mantle temperatures that conflict with observations [13]. Recent work has identified a zone within the central mare region that exhibits high elevations relative to the rest of the maria, extensional tectonics consistent with surface uplift, elevated Th concentrations, and relatively young mare volcanism [14]. These observations are consistent with this region being underlain by the present-day KREEP reservoir. The location of this reservoir, in an arc circumferential to Imbrium but far beyond the excavated zone, is consistent with models that predict that basin-scale impacts generate thermal anomalies that would displace upper mantle material radially outwards [10].

Figure 5. The central mare elevated region (dashed outline) shows geophysical, tectonic, and compositional signatures consistent with an underlying KREEP reservoir [14].

Summary: Nearly every aspect of lunar evolution has been affected by the solidification of the lunar magma ocean and subsequent evolution of the late-stage magma ocean products. While much uncertainty remains, a variety of observations and models enable us to piece together a self-consistent understanding of the evolution through space and time of the late-stage magma ocean and its crystallization products.

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